

Influence of Temperature on the Setting of Inorganic Jellies.

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In previous publications from this laboratory (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **6**, 391, 587; *ibid.*, 1930, **7**, 367, 417, 591; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1931, **201**, 301.) we have investigated the preparation and properties of a number of inorganic jellies. We have also studied (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, **34**, 954) the influence of temperature on the coagulation of various sols and have shown that such sols as hydrous oxides of iron, chromium, tin and aluminium become comparatively unstable when the temperature is raised, whilst easily hydrolysable sols such as prussian blue, gamboge and mastic are stabilised at higher temperatures.

In this communication, we are recording our observations on the influence of temperature on the setting of various jellies. The jelly-forming mixtures were prepared at ordinary temperatures and divided into three portions, and they were allowed to set in thermostats maintained at three different temperatures. The time of setting of the jellies was noted in every case. The setting point of a jelly was sharp enough to take readings with an accuracy of 10 seconds.

The jellies were prepared by methods described in foregoing papers. Where the jellies were obtained by coagulation, the sols were dialysed for such periods as were necessary to produce jellies of the best texture. So long as the sols were comparatively impure, either no jelles were formed or they gave loose opaque coagulum. In no case the sols could be completely freed from electrolytic impurities, as there was an apprehension of the spontaneous setting of sols to jellies by dialysis alone.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Zirconium Hydroxide Jelly.

The jelly was prepared by the addition of various quantities of 3.84*N*-sodium acetate to 3 c. c. of 10% zirconium nitrate

solution, and the volume was made up to 5 c. c. in every case. The mixtures were allowed to set at 30°, 50° and 70°. The results are recorded in the following table.

TABLE I.

	Time of setting.		
	30°	50°	70°
0.348N-sodium acetate			
0.1 c. c.	No jelly	No jelly	No jelly.
0.2	Do	Do	Do
0.3	Do	Do	Do
0.4	3 hrs.	6 mins.	35 sec.
0.5	2 mins.	30 secs.	Immediately.

The results recorded in this table show that below a certain minimum concentration of sodium acetate, no jelly is formed even at higher temperatures. The time of setting of the jelly is markedly decreased at higher temperatures.

Zirconium Borate Jelly.

The jelly was prepared by dialysing for four days the sol obtained by mixing saturated borax solution with 10% zirconium nitrate solution and coagulating the sol by different amounts of N/5 potassium sulphate.

Concentration of the sol = 24.72 g. zirconium borate per litre.
Amount of sol taken = 3 c. c. Total volume = 5 c. c.

TABLE II.

	Time of setting.		
	30°	50°	70°
N/5-K ₂ SO ₄ .			
0.4 c. c.	2 hrs.	30 mins.	15 mins.
0.5	16 min.	12	5
0.6	13	11	1
0.7	No jelly but ppt.	4	30 sec.
0.8	No jelly but ppt.	No jelly but ppt.	20 sec. the jelly soon synerises.

Zirconium Molybdate Jelly.

The sol of zirconium molybdate was prepared by mixing 3% potassium molybdate solution with 10% zirconium nitrate solution and dialysing the mixture for 5 days. Concentration of the sol was 14.48 g. zirconium molybdate per litre. The jellies were prepared by coagulating the sol with different amounts of *N/50* potassium sulphate.

Amount of sol taken = 10 c. c. Total volume = 12 c. c.

TABLE III.

<i>N/50-K₂SO₄</i>	Time of setting.		
	30°	50°	70°
1.2 c. c.	No jelly	2 hrs. 30 min.	10 min.
1.3	5 hrs.	1 hr. 20 min.	6
1.4	3 hrs. 15 min.	1 hr.	5
1.5	1 hr. 25 min.	29 min	4
1.6	45 min.	22 min	2

Thorium Arsenate Jelly.

This jelly was obtained by mixing different concentrations of 18% potassium arsenate solution with 10 c. c. of thorium nitrate (12.06 g. of the salt per litre), the solution being made up to 12 c.c. in every case.

TABLE IV.

18% <i>KH₂SO₄</i>	Time of setting.		
	30°	40°	45°
0.7 c. c.	1 day	No jelly	No jelly
0.8	2 hrs.	Do	Do
0.9	25 min.	Loose jelly in 2½ hrs.	Do
1.0	18	35 min.	2 hrs.
1.1	5	26 min.	90 min.

When the temperature was raised above 50°, the thorium arsenate mixture did not yield any jelly, not even when kept for

five hours. However, if the jelly-forming mixtures be again brought to 30°, they set to jellies.

Thorium Phosphate Jelly.

The jellies of thorium phosphate were prepared by adding varying amounts of 11% potassium phosphate solution to 10 c. c. of thorium nitrate solution (12.06 g. per litre). The total volume was made up to 12 c. c. in every case.

TABLE V.

11% KH_2PO_4 .	Time of setting.		
	30°	40°	45°
0.8 c. c.	No jelly	No jelly	No jelly
0.9	120 min.	66 min.	58 min.
1.0	48	24	20
1.1	16	10	7
1.2	2	2	2

Thorium Molybdate Jelly.

These jellies were prepared by adding varying amounts of 4.5% potassium molybdate to 10 c. c. of thorium nitrate solution containing 12.06 g. of the salt per 250 c. c.

Total volume = 12 c. c.

TABLE VI.

4.5% K_2MoO_4 .	Time of setting.		
	30°	50°	70°
0.9 c. c.	> 60 min.	30 min.	22 min.
1.0	> 60	25	16
1.1	33	20	11
1.2	30	18	10
1.3	28	15	8

Chromium Arsenate Jelly.

The sol was prepared by dialysing the mixture of 100 c. c. of $M/2$ -chromic chloride and 80 c. c. of 18% potassium arsenate

solution for 6 days. It set to jellies when coagulated with *N/5* potassium sulphate.

TABLE VII.

Concentration of the sol = 36.4 g. per litre.
Amount of sol taken = 10 c. c. Total volume = 15 c. c.

<i>N/5</i> -K ₂ SO ₄	Time of setting.		
	30°	50°	70°
2.2 c. c	54 min.	10 min.	1 min.
2.3	36	4	1
2.4	22	3	50 sec.
2.5	15	2	80 sec.
2.6	Ppt.	Ppt.	Ppt.

Vanadium Pentoxide Jelly.

Vanadic acid was precipitated by adding concentrated hydrochloric acid to ammonium vanadate. The precipitate on careful washing passed into a clear red sol, which set to jellies when coagulated with potassium chloride. Concentration of the sol was 1.92 g. vanadium pentoxide per litre.

Amount of sol taken = 5 c. c. Total volume = 12 c. c.

TABLE VIII.

<i>N/20</i> -KCl.	Time of setting.		
	30°	50°	70°
1.0 c.c	3 hrs. 20 min.	No jelly in 3 hrs.	No jelly in 3 hrs.
1.2	88 min.	No jelly in 3 hrs	No jelly
1.3	20	100 min.	Do
1.4	13	45	Do
1.5	4	30	150 min.

Mercuri-sulphosalicylic Acid Jelly.

Mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid was prepared by dissolving 1.5 mols of mercuric oxide in 1 mol. of sulphosalicylic acid and drying the mixture on a water-bath. One gram of the powder thus obtained

was dissolved in 100 c. c. of water. A clear sol with slight opalescence was obtained which set to jellies on addition of $N\text{-K}_2\text{SO}_4$.

8 c. c. of 1% mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid were taken every time and the total volume was made up to 10 c. c.

TABLE IX.

$N\text{-K}_2\text{SO}_4$.	Time of setting.		
	30°	40°	50°
0.4	No jelly	No jelly	No jelly
0.5	18 min.	Do	Do
0.6	10	30 min.	Do
0.7	7	15	Do
1.0	1	2	Loose jelly in 8 min.

Zinc Arsenate Jelly.

Zinc arsenate jellies were prepared by taking 5 c. c. of zinc sulphate solution (14.368 g. in 250 c. c.) and adding an equal quantity of water to it and then mixing it with different amounts of 18% potassium arsenate solution. The the total volume was made up to 20 c. c. in every case.

TABLE X.

18% KH_2AsO_4 .	Time of setting.		
	30°	50°	70°
0.16	Did not set	Loose jelly in 60 sec.	Ppt.
0.18	„	90 sec.	30 sec.
0.20	„	60	5
0.30	5 sec.	5	5

Stannic Arsenate Jelly.

To 2 or 3 c.c. of $M/1.099$ -stannic chloride solution were added the varying concentrations of 18% potassium arsenate solution and the total volume was made up to 6 c.c. in every case. A set of the mixture was allowed to set at 20° while the other set was warmed for 5 minutes at 90° and then transferred to ordinary room temperature (20°). The time of gelation was noted in every case.

TABLE XI.

<i>M</i> /1·099-Stannic chloride.	18% Potassium arsenate.	Time of setting.	
		20°	90° (warming)
3·0 c.c.	1 c.c.	23 hrs.	10 hrs.
3·0	2	90 min.	6 min.
3·0	3	25 min.	3
2·0	0·5	24 hrs.	5

The marked temperature influence observed in the case of this substance is probably due to the fact that warming for a few minutes at a higher temperature causes the hydrolysis of stannic arsenate to stannic oxide. The oxide is also known to yield fine jellies which under the circumstances may set more rapidly than the arsenate jelly.

Stannic Phosphate Jelly.

3 C.c. of *M*/1·099-stannic chloride solution were mixed with varying amounts of 22 per cent. potassium phosphate solution and the total volume was made up to 6 c.c. in every case. One set of the mixture was allowed to set at 20° while the other at 90°.

TABLE XII.

22% KH_2PO_4 .	Time of setting.	
	20°	90°
0·5 c.c.	22 hrs.	5 min.
1·0	2 hrs.	3
1·5	30 min.	2
2·0	18	1

Stannic Tungstate Jelly.

1·5 or 2 c.c. of 1·53*M* stannic chloride solution were mixed with different concentrations of 15% sodium tungstate solution. The total volume was made up to 6 c.c. in every case. The mixtures were shaken for five minutes and then transferred to baths at 20° and 93° and the time of gelation was observed.

TABLE XIII.

1.53M-Stannic chloride.	15% Sodium tungstate.	Time of setting	
		20°	93°
2 c.c.	2.0 c.c.	No jelly	No jelly
2	2.5	No jelly	20 min.
2	3.0	5 days	8
2	3.5	2 days	6
1.5	2.0	>5 hrs.	8

Stannic Molybdate Jelly.

A mixture of stannic chloride in excess and potassium molybdate was dialysed for 24 hours. Concentration of the sol was 91.04 g. SnO₂ per litre. This sol when half diluted gave jellies at different temperatures as follows :

TABLE XIV.

Temp.	...	90°	70°	60°	50°	40°	24°
Time of gelation in min.	...	1	2	4	7	20	360.

Discussion.

The results recorded in the foregoing tables show that in the case of zirconium hydroxide, zirconium molybdate, zirconium borate, thorium molybdate, thorium phosphate, chromium tungstate, stannic arsenate, phosphate, tungstate and molybdate, the time of setting markedly decreases as the temperature is raised.

The jellies of thorium arsenate, vanadium pentoxide and mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid take a longer time to set at higher temperatures, and above a certain temperature, they do not set at all.

No systematic work appears to have been done before on the influence of temperature on the formation of jellies. Fleming (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1902, **41**, 427) and Holmes (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1918, **22**, 516) observed that a slight increase in temperature accelerates the time of setting of silicic acid jelly, while Falls and Firth (*ibid.*, 1925, **29**, 243) did not observe any distinct variation with temperature over the range from 0° to 45°. Conflicting results are also found in the case of manganous arsenate jellies (*cf.* Deiss, *Kolloid. Z.*, 1914, **14**, 139; and Kraemer, *Colloid Symp. Monograph*, Wisconsin, 1923, **1**, 66). We have observed that if the manganous chloride and potassium arsenate mixture is warmed at 60° to 80°, it will form manganous

Ratio of velocities.	If directly proportional to the change in intensity.	If proportional to the square root of the change in intensity.
$\frac{\text{Vel. I}}{\text{Vel. II}} = \frac{0\cdot000422}{0\cdot000174} = 2\cdot43$	$\frac{3\cdot14}{0\cdot5024} = 6\cdot25$	2·5
$\frac{\text{Vel. II}}{\text{Vel. III}} = \frac{0\cdot000174}{0\cdot000094} = 1\cdot9$	$\frac{0\cdot5024}{0\cdot1256} = 4$	2
$\frac{\text{Vel. I}}{\text{Vel. III}} = \frac{0\cdot000422}{0\cdot000094} = 4\cdot5$	$\frac{3\cdot14}{0\cdot1256} = 25$	5

Hence the reaction between citric acid and chromic acid is proportional to the square root of the change in intensity.

6. N/4·27 Tartaric acid and N/44·4 Chromic acid, 10 c. c. each.

Source of light:—1000 watt gas filled tungsten filament lamp.

Temperature = 32°. Dark:— $k_1 = 0\cdot00305$.

Diameter of the aperture.	k_1 Monomolecular.	True light reaction.
2 cm.	0·00705	0·00400
0·8 cm.	0·00467	0·00162
0·4 cm.	0·00385	0·00080

Ratio of velocities.	If directly proportional to the change in intensity.	If proportional to the square root of the change in intensity.
$\frac{\text{Vel. I}}{\text{Vel. II}} = \frac{0\cdot0040}{0\cdot00162} = 2\cdot46$	$\frac{3\cdot14}{0\cdot5024} = 6\cdot25$	2·5
$\frac{\text{Vel. II}}{\text{Vel. III}} = \frac{0\cdot00162}{0\cdot00080} = 2\cdot0$	$\frac{0\cdot5024}{0\cdot1256} = 4$	2
$\frac{\text{Vel. I}}{\text{Vel. III}} = \frac{0\cdot0040}{0\cdot00080} = 5$	$\frac{3\cdot14}{0\cdot1256} = 25$	5

Hence the reaction between tartaric acid and chromic acid is proportional to the square root of the change in intensity.

7. N/4.72 Lactic acid and N/44.4 Chromic acid, 10 c.c. each.

Source of light:—1000 watt gas filled tungsten filament lamp.

Temperature = 32°. Dark:— $k_1 = 0.00195$.

Diameter of the aperture.	k_1 Monomolecular.	True light reaction.
2 cm.	0.00358	0.00163
0.8 cm.	0.00222	0.00027
0.4 cm.	0.00202	0.00007
Ratio of velocities.	If directly proportional to the change in intensity.	If proportional to the square root of the change in intensity.
$\frac{\text{Vel. I}}{\text{Vel. II}} = \frac{0.00163}{0.00027} = 6$	$\frac{3.14}{0.5024} = 6.25$	2.5
$\frac{\text{Vel. II}}{\text{Vel. III}} = \frac{0.00027}{0.00007} = 3.85$	$\frac{0.5024}{0.1256} = 4$	2
$\frac{\text{Vel. I}}{\text{Vel. III}} = \frac{0.00163}{0.00007} = 23.3$	$\frac{3.14}{0.1256} = 25$	5

Hence the reaction between lactic acid and chromic acid is directly proportional to the change in intensity.

Discussion.

The experimental results show that the decomposition of ferric thiocyanate, the bleaching of neocyanin, the reactions between citric acid and chromic acid, and tartaric acid and chromic acid are practically proportional to the square root of the intensity of the incident radiation. On the other hand, the reactions between sodium lactate and iodine, sodium tartrate and iodine and chromic acid and lactic acid are practically directly proportional to the change in the intensity of the incident radiation. In presence of sunlight the reactions between chromic acid and the organic acids follow the same relations as in the case of light from the tungsten filament lamp.

The velocity measurements show that the first group of reactions is largely accelerated by light. The reactions between chromic acid and tartaric acid, and chromic acid and citric acid have been found to be more accelerated by light than the reaction between chromic acid and lactic acid. In other words, the thermal reactions are slow in comparison with the reactions in light only. In these reactions many molecules are readily activated by the absorption of radiation on illumination and consequently further increase in light intensity is not likely to increase the velocity of reaction markedly, because the number of inactive molecules available for further activation is small. Consequently those reactions, which are highly photochemical in nature, have much less chance of showing direct proportionality between the incident light and the velocity of reactions. On the other hand, the second group of reactions are only feebly accelerated by light and in this group the number of inactive molecules which are capable of being activated on increased illumination are much larger than in the first group of reactions. Consequently the velocity of these reactions will increase proportionately as the intensity of the incident radiation is increased. These relations would be observed when the incident radiation is appreciably absorbed by the reacting system. If the reacting system markedly absorb the incident radiation, direct proportionality or even square of the intensity may be expected because a marked increase in intensity and hence amount of light will lead to an increased velocity of the reaction, but if we are considering a reaction which is fast in the dark or is largely accelerated by light increased absorption of light cannot cause a concomitant increase in the velocity of the reaction because the number of molecules available for activation due to absorption of light is small. Hence, even in those reactions where the incident radiation is markedly absorbed but are largely activated by light and are highly photosensitive, instead of direct proportionality, square root relation is obtained. We find that these considerations can satisfactorily explain our experimental results obtained with about 30 reactions investigated in these laboratories.

The reaction between potassium oxalate and iodine is proportional to the square root of the incident radiation, whereas the reaction between sodium lactate and iodine is directly proportional to the intensity. If we assume that in presence of light a molecule of iodine is atomised, we can explain the intensity effect on the

reaction between potassium oxalate and iodine but this conception that the halogen molecules are atomised on illumination does not help us in understanding the mechanism of those photochemical reactions with halogens as one of the reacting substances and where the velocity of reaction is directly proportional to the intensity of incident light. Our experimental results show that the reaction between sodium lactate and iodine is only slightly accelerated by light and consequently the inactive molecules available for activation on illumination is large and consequently a direct proportionality is observed. We are of the opinion that this explanation of the difference of intensity effect on different reactions is more satisfactory than any of the existing views.

In numerous publications from these laboratories we have shown that the temperature coefficient of a photochemical reaction is smaller than the temperature coefficient of the reaction in the dark, and the greater the acceleration produced by light, the less the lowering of the temperature coefficient; consequently, in those reactions where the velocity is directly proportional to the intensity of incident radiation, the lowering of temperature coefficient due to light will be less than in those reactions where the velocities are more or less proportional to the square root of the intensity of incident radiation. Hence we are in a position to predict the intensity effect on a photochemical reaction by measurement of its speed and temperature coefficient in light and in the dark.

Summary.

1. The influence of the variation of the intensity of the radiation from a 1000 watt gas filled tungsten filament lamp was investigated on seven photochemical reactions.

2. The experiments show that the velocities of the following reactions are proportional to the square root of the incident radiation:—(a) Decomposition of ferric thiocyanate; (b) bleaching of neocyanin; (c) reactions between citric acid and chromic acid, and (d) tartaric acid and chromic acid.

The velocities of the following reactions are directly proportional to the intensity of the radiation:—

(a) Sodium lactate and iodine; (b) sodium tartrate and iodine; (c) lactic acid and chromic acid.

3. The two important factors, which are of consequence in the relation between intensity and the velocity of a reaction, are:—(1) amount of absorption of the incident radiation by the reacting system, and (2) the acceleration of the reaction in presence of light. When the absorption of radiation is high and the reaction is not markedly photochemical in nature and the velocity of the reaction in the dark is appreciable, direct proportionality or even square of intensity is likely to be observed. On the other hand, when the reaction is highly photochemical in nature and the velocity of the dark reaction is practically negligible, square root relation will be expected.

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